

ЕКОНОМІКА ТА УПРАВЛІННЯ

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DIRECTIONS OF EXTREME TOURISM IN UKRAINE

Purpose. In the world market of tourist services the extreme tourism is very popular, as it does not require the significant financial costs and enables year on year to increase the offers of holiday packages, associated with active travel. Ukraine has significant potential for the development of extreme kinds of rest, but it is not developed enough. Forms of extreme tourism are unknown for domestic tourists, and therefore, they formed a negative attitude. The aim of the article is the analysis of extreme resort potential of Ukraine and promotion of the development of extreme tourism destinations in the travel market. Theoretical and methodological basis of research is the system analysis of the problems of ensuring the competitiveness of the tourism industry, theoretical principles of economic science in the field of the effectiveness of extreme tourism and management of tourist flows. **Methodology.** The author offers the directions of tourist flows control, which differ from the current expansion of services to tourists in Ukraine. The development of extreme tourism with the help of co-operation of railways and sport federations was proposed. **Findings.** During the research the author proved that the implementation of the tasks will be promote: 1) increase in budget revenues at all levels of the inner extreme tourism; 2) raise the image of Ukraine and Ukrainian Railways; 3) increase the share of tourism and resorts in the gross domestic product to the level of developed countries; 4) bringing the number of employees in tourism and resorts to the level of developed countries; 5) the creation of an effective system of monitoring the quality of tourist services; 6) the creation of an attractive investment climate for attracting the investment in the broad development of tourism, engineering and transport and municipal infrastructure; 7) improvement the safety of tourists, ensure the effective protection of their rights and legitimate interests and preservation of the property. **Originality.** The author shows the theoretical generalization and new solution of a scientific problem. It manifests itself in the development of theoretical and methodological approaches to the development of extreme tourism. **Practical value.** Rational use of measures proposed by the author of directional control of tourist flows will significantly increase the country's revenues from domestic tourism.

Keywords: railway tourism; tourist flow; tourist route; extreme tourism; resort potential

Introduction

Extreme tourism is a type of tourism that is associated with a certain degree of risk, or with prohibitive physical or mental strain and stress in tough conditions.

The main thing in extreme tourism is natural settings for a selected type of holiday and experienced managers. All routes of extreme tourism have different categories of complexity. The majority does not require the years of experience and thorough

preparation, and usually they are under the power of any healthy active person. [3].

Mountain climbing, jeep tours, kayaking, diving, paragliding, rafting, industrial and mountaineering are the most popular forms of recreation.

Some travel companies offer to demanding tourists the exotic tourism. This could be a fly on the Earth's orbit, the descent from the mountains on a motorcycle, hunting for sharks under the water, traveling in the dungeon and descend from the sand dunes on a snowboard and other [2].

If not to take into account that the exotic tourism is expensive, we can say that an extreme tourism refers to one of the most attractive tourist recreation, because the most travelers want not only to see but to feel it. People go on holiday for emotions. They are willing to spend money for the positive and sometimes unusual emotions [13].

Problems and prospects of the extreme tourism development were studied by such scholars as I. Svida, A. Romanov, Yu. Dmytriiievskiy, Ya. Arin, V. Huliiiev. Their works analyse the foreign development of recreation extreme forms, but as for Ukraine, this area still requires the further research study.

Purpose

The article aim is to analyse the development of extreme resort potential of Ukraine and popularizing of extreme tourism destinations in the travel market.

Methodology

Ukraine has the considerable potential for extreme forms of recreation, but it is underdeveloped. The forms of extreme tourism is largely unknown to domestic tourists, so they formed inert or negative attitude.

But the global tourism industry is constantly developing and offering the new services to all tourists [1]. In recent times the great demand for not only the usual sightseeing trips and also tourism associated with the recreational activities. Ukraine has enough places where the extreme tourism can be organized. The klondike of ideas embodiment in this context can and should become Zakarpattia, Lviv and Ivano-Frankivsk region.

Each year in the Zakarpattia region the extreme competitions are hold. Among the popular places of the organized extreme sport are Mukachevo, Uzhgorod and surroundings of the Borzhava River.

Among the most popular forms of extreme tourism in our country are: mountaineering and mountain hiking; caving; skiing; white-water rafting (rafting on mountain rivers); paragliding and hang gliding.

In the Zakarpattia region the mountainous kinds of extreme tourism are popular. The most extreme form of recreation is considered the mountaineering; the tourists overcome various obstacles of varying degrees of severity.

The Carpathian mountains, located on the territory of Zakarpattia region, are relatively safe and there is the possibility to organize the climbing routes of varying difficulty. The Caucasus or the Urals are famous for the sharp slopes and dips, so to organize tours there is not the most profitable business. In Zakarpattia, if exclude from the tourist routes the most rugged mountains Gorgan, all other mountains in the region can be considered as suitable for the development of mountaineering. Today the most visited mountains are located in Volovetsk, Mizhhirsk, Rakhivsk, Velykoberezniansk, Svaliavsk and Mukachivsk districts [4].

The popularity of skiing and snowboarding increases from year to year. The highest ski base of Ukrainian Carpathians is Drahobrat where the two rope tows kilometer long lead from the height of over 1,300 m near the Stig mountain (1704 m).

If to remember the climbing routes, the hundreds of them are laid in the Smotrych canyon. There the rock canyon was washed with the Smotrych River, which forms the open loop around the old city. The height of the cliffs in the canyon reaches fifty meters.

The terrestrial kinds of extreme tourism include caving, horse riding and hunting tourism, pedestrian and combined bus-hiking, mountbiking, X-racing, sport orienteering, avtotour, rally, mototourism and survival in the wild.

As for caving, there are dozens of caves in the Zakarpattia region. The most popular among tourists are the caves near the settlements Kniahynia, Mala Uholka and cave «Druzhba», located in Tiachivsk district.

As for equestrian, hunting and walking tourism, they certainly can be developed throughout the Ukraine, because in our country there is an enough necessary resource potential. Tourists can be offered the combined tours – the combination of several kinds of active rest in one route, such as tracking and equestrian tourism.

Findings

Today in the world market of tourist services very popular is tourism on particularly dangerous routes.

Here is a short list of the popular kinds of extreme tourism in other countries.

Thus, Turkey is famous for diving. Places for diving are incredibly much. The most popular is

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considered Bordum, Cargo and Kecek islands. On the way to the islands are beautiful underwater reefs. Catal Island is a favorite place for fans of underwater archeology. Thus here is the world's only museum of underwater treasure. Also in Turkey, there are many proposals for travel on mountain river. The most popular place for rafting fans is the mountain river Dalaman [8].

Egypt also attracts tourists with diving and exotic journey through the desert. Thailand is famous for water tourism. Spain captures with Bullfighting. Travel Agency in South America offering acquaintance with the Indian tribes. Switzerland develops the gliding and climbing actively. In Africa the tourists are offered the safari in the national parks, rafting the Nile or climbing peaks in African mountains. The trips to wild places are very popular [7]. In China, the tourists have the opportunity to learn about the ancient Chinese culture, religion, ancient monuments and exotic cuisine. Diving is pretty developed. India will delight tourists with windsurfing. More and more wishing to go to extreme climatic conditions in cruises to the Arctic and Antarctic and look at exotic animals, for example Penguins. According to statistics, one third of holidaymakers weekly go on safari or ride on a yacht, or have other recreational activities in Europe [10].

If to go back to Ukraine, it can be emphasized that in this country there are all opportunities for the development of some types of extreme tourism, but the public authorities are not given enough attention on this problem. In addition, in Ukraine the lack of objective information about the safety and availability of extreme sports encourage the domestic tourists to seek such services in other countries. Do not forget about the worsening of social and economic situation in the country, where the cost of basic necessities need to be increased, and costs on holidays are reduced accordingly. However, in Ukraine there is the resource potential for the organization of recreation available to the wider population [5].

For example, mountain bike is the downhill from the mountain on a bike, the overcoming obstacles through stones, high-speed travel through dangerous places, fast ride around the track with jumps and other obstacles.

The sport orienteering with a map and a compass can be interesting for Ukrainians. In Zakarpattia the sport orienteering competitions can be organized in the area of the Nevitskij castle.

In Zakarpattia region are the ideal preconditions for this extraordinary sport like hang-gliding and paragliding. The most favorable conditions are the territory of Rakhiv, Perechyn, Velykobereznianskyi and partially in other areas [7].

The water extreme tourism can be developed: the descent on mountain rivers by canoe. In Zakarpattia, the descent on mountain rivers by canoe can be organized (Vynohradivsk, Perechynsk, Velykoberezniansk and Uzhhorod areas) [8].

Do not forget about such a romantic and extreme kind of the rest as flying on balloons. There are excellent natural conditions for the development of aeronautics in Ukraine. The flights over the megacities above the beautiful historical places, which in our country are enough can be organized. Today in Ukraine about twenty balloons are only used that is in twenty times less than in Russia and Holland and in the three hundred times (!) in comparison with Germany.

Among the extreme kinds of sport is skydiving. So far, this kind of extreme sports is at an early stage of development in Ukraine.

Today in Ukraine there are only three large dropzones: two in Kyiv and one near Dnipropetrovsk, which is in twenty times less than in the UK.

The rafting is one of the popular kinds of sport nowadays in other countries and perspective for the development in Ukraine. Our lowland rivers without rapids are suited very well for raftings of ordinary people and not for athletes training. For the adventure-seekers the Pivdennyi Buh with its rapids and shallows will be a good variant, and for the most experienced the mountain rivers of Carpathians.

Safari is a fascinating experience. And if in the last century, it meant the hunting wild African animals, with the advent of modern photography Safari can be a photo or video hunting that is not harmful to living creatures.

Ukraine is also famous with its reserves. Today there are 17 natures, 4 biosphere reserves and 12 national parks in which the wildlife is protected by the State. Askania-Nova is one of the largest biological reserves in Europe, which collected the animals-representatives of almost all continents of the planet [6].

Carpathians and Precarpathians are promising areas for development of extreme tourism in the Ukrainian. Places of the photo hunt development can be: national nature parks Vyzhnytsk, Hutsulshchyna and Carpathian biosphere reserve. Aeronautics is promising to be developed in the area of the canyon valley of the middle reaches of the Dniester River with wonderful views of historic places of Khotyn and Kamenets-Podilskyi fortresses.

Originality and practical value

Ukraine with its resource potential is a country of great opportunities for the organization of active and extreme rest.

The tourist can be attracted with the element of novelty, stress and release of energy excess and the financially availability.

The railway tourist company together with the sports federations can organize the extreme tours [11].

The railway can arrange the delivery to the place of extreme kinds of tourism and accommodation in comfortable cars (among other benefits: savings in hotels and restaurants, essential travel can begin from the moment of boarding the car, accessibility from a financial point of view), and representatives of sports clubs will be responsible for the proper conduct of specific activities.

In the course of the study the list of factors that is included in the economic category «the attractiveness of the route of a tourist trip» was further developed, these factors are: most convenient time of the passenger trip, comfort of rolling stock, the number of stops and attraction sites of historical, natural and cultural heritage that will be used to set the category of the route and predict the economic efficiency of travel.

Conclusions

The world extreme tourism is growing rapidly, but Ukraine is significantly far behind the developed countries [12].

However, with well-organized approach the development of extreme tourism of the domestic tourism market is very promising.

The low level of development the tourism infrastructure and social standards of the population hinders the development of adventure

tourism in Ukraine. According to many domestic experts, there is a great potential for the extreme tourism, which can be opened with the general social and economic development of the State.

In Ukraine the development of such types of extreme tourism, as ballooning, parachute jumping, caving, rafting and safaris is considered promising.

Domestic tourism can be developed with the help of extreme tourism, and with the competent information policy and sufficient level of service the rapid development of international tourism can be expected. The proposed activities will contribute to the increase of incomes of the different levels budgets and the promotion of the country on the world market of tourist services.

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НАПРАВЛЕННЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ЭКСТРЕМАЛЬНОГО ТУРИЗМА В УКРАИНЕ

Цель. На мировом рынке туристических услуг экстремальный туризм пользуется большой популярностью, так как он не требует значительных финансовых затрат и позволяет из года в год в несколько раз увеличить пакеты предложений отдыха, связанного с активными путешествиями. В Украине есть значительный потенциал для развития экстремальных видов отдыха, однако он недостаточно развит. Формы экстремального туризма являются малоизвестными для отечественных туристов, поэтому к ним сформировано негативное отношение. Целью статьи является анализ экстремально-курортного потенциала Украины и разработка направлений популяризации экстремального туризма на рынке туристических услуг. Теоретическую и методологическую основу исследования составляют системный анализ проблем обеспечения конкурентоспособности туристической отрасли, теоретические положения экономической науки в области эффективности экстремального туризма и управления туристическими потоками. **Методика.** Автором предложены направления управления туристическими потоками, которые отличаются от существующих расширением сферы услуг туристам на территории Украины. Предложено развитие экстремального туризма с помощью кооперации железнодорожных компаний и спортивных федераций. **Результаты.** В ходе проведения исследования автором доказано, что выполнение поставленных задач будет содействовать: 1) увеличению доходов бюджетов всех уровней от внутреннего экстремального туризма; 2) повышению имиджа страны и украинских железных дорог; 3) повышению доли сферы туризма и курортов в структуре валового внутреннего продукта до уровня развитых стран; 4) доведению количества работников сферы туризма и курортов до уровня развитых стран; 5) созданию эффективной системы мониторинга качества туристических услуг; 6) созданию привлекательного инвестиционного климата для широкого привлечения инвестиций в развитие туристической, инженерно-транспортной и коммунальной инфраструктуры; 7) повышению безопасности туристов, обеспечению действенной защиты их прав, законных интересов и сохранения имущества. **Научная новизна.** Автором приведены теоретическое обобщение и новое решение научной задачи. Она проявляется в разработке теоретических и методологических подходов к необходимости развития экстремального туризма. **Практическая значимость.** Рационально примененные меры по предложенным автором направлениям управления туристическими потоками позволят существенно повысить поступления в бюджет страны от внутреннего туризма.

Ключевые слова: железнодорожный туризм; туристический поток; туристический маршрут; экстремальный туризм; курортный потенциал

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НАПРЯМКИ РОЗВИТКУ ЕКСТРЕМАЛЬНОГО ТУРИЗМУ В УКРАЇНІ

Мета. На світовому ринку туристичних послуг екстремальний туризм користується великим попитом, тому що він не потребує значних фінансових витрат та дозволяє з року в рік у декілька разів збільшити пакети пропозицій відпочинку, пов'язаного з активними подорожами. В Україні є значний потенціал для розвитку екстремальних видів відпочинку, проте він недостатньо розвинений. Форми екстремального туризму є маловідомими для вітчизняних туристів, тому до них сформоване негативне ставлення. Метою статті є аналіз екстремально-курортного потенціалу України та розробка напрямків популяризації екстремального туризму на ринку туристичних послуг. Теоретичну та методологічну основу дослідження становлять системний аналіз проблем забезпечення конкурентоспроможності туристичної галузі, теоретичні положення економічної науки в галузі ефективності екстремального туризму й управління туристичними потоками. **Методика.** Автором запропоновано напрямки управління туристичними потоками, які відрізняються від існуючих розширенням сфери послуг туристам на території України. Запропоновано розвиток екстремального туризму за допомогою кооперації залізничних компаній та спортивних федерацій. **Результати.** У ході проведення досліджень автором доведено, що виконання поставлених завдань сприятиме: 1) збільшенню доходів бюджетів усіх рівнів від внутрішнього екстремального туризму; 2) підвищенню іміджу країни та українських залізниць; 3) підвищенню частки сфери туризму і курортів у структурі валового внутрішнього продукту до рівня розвинутих країн; 4) доведенню кількості працівників сфери туризму та курортів до рівня розвинутих країн; 5) створенню ефективної системи моніторингу якості туристичних послуг; 6) створенню привабливого інвестиційного клімату для широкого залучення інвестицій у розвиток туристичної, інженерно-транспортної та комунальної інфраструктури; 7) підвищенню безпеки туристів, забезпеченню дієвого захисту їхніх прав, законних інтересів і збереження майна. **Наукова новизна.** Автором наведено теоретичне узагальнення й нове вирішення наукової задачі. Вона виявляється в розробці теоретичних і методологічних підходів щодо необхідності розвитку екстремального туризму. **Практична значимість.** Рационально застосовані заходи за запропонованими автором напрямками управління туристичними потоками дозволять суттєво підвищити надходження до бюджету країни від внутрішнього туризму.

Ключові слова: залізничний туризм; туристичний потік; туристичний маршрут; екстремальний туризм; курортний потенціал

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